

CELLULOSIC NANOCOMPOSITE PREPARED BY ACETYLATION OF BACTERIAL CELLULOSE USING SUPERCRITICAL CARBON DIOXIDE

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SUMMARY

The surface of bacterial cellulose (BC) nanofibers was acetylated under supercritical carbon dioxide (sc-CO₂) condition without using organic solvent. The BC nanofibers, with their surface selectively acetylated, were compression molded into the composite. This new type all-cellulose composite was found to possess high optical transparency, mechanical properties and heat resistance.

Keywords: Acetylation, Bacterial cellulose, Supercritical carbon dioxide, All-cellulose composite, Environmentally friendly

INTRODUCTION

Cellulose is the most abundant natural homopolymer, and it plays a significant role in the structural support of plant cell walls because of its high mechanical properties [1]. The maximum macroscopic Young's modulus of plant cellulose (up to 128GPa [2]) is higher than those (ca. 70GPa) of aluminum and glass fiber. In addition, the elastic modulus E_t of the crystalline regions of cellulose I is 138GPa [3]. This excellent mechanical property of cellulose is due to its high degree of polymerization, the linear orientation of its molecules, and hydrogen bonds, which stabilize the molecule itself and connect it tightly to neighboring ones. The excellent mechanical property of cellulose has brought about the current trend toward eco-composites focusing on the best use of cellulose fibers, e.g., poly-L-lactic acid reinforced with natural plant fiber (hemp, [4] kenaf, [5] flax, [6] etc.).

In general, composites are composed of two chemically different materials. The interface between the incorporated fiber and the matrix often causes problems, such as poor compatibility, insufficient stress transfer, and high water uptake. If the fiber and the matrix are both made of the same material, benefits such as recyclability and good adhesion through the perfect interface can be expected. We reported the development of a novel material, an all-cellulose composite, in which the incorporated fibers and the matrix were both made of cellulose [7-10]. It was prepared by impregnating the cellulose solution into uniaxially aligned cellulose fibers [7] or selectively dissolving of fibers surface, then dried [8-10]. These all-cellulose composites had excellent mechanical properties and thermal performance. Cellulose is well known that it does not melt but degrades at high temperature. Thus in order for processing cellulose, organic solvent is needed even for preparing all-cellulose composite. However, from the view

point of environmental issues, not only the final product, but also the process should be environmentally friendly.

In this study, we developed an environmentally friendly process for the preparation of the all-cellulose composite without using organic solvent. The surface of cellulose fibers was acetylated under super critical carbon dioxide (sc-CO₂) condition. The cellulose fibers, with their surface selectively acetylated, were compression molded. Then the new type all-cellulose composite, made of residual cellulose core fiber as reinforcement and cellulose acetate (CA) as matrix, was obtained. Especially, we selected bacterial cellulose (BC) as a starting material. The structure and properties of this Eco and Nano composite were investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sample Preparation

The cellulose nanofiber employed in this study is BC (Fujicco, Ltd.). The dried sheet-like BC, being pretreated with ZnCl₂ aq. soln., was sealed with acetic anhydride, in a high pressure reactor, then pressured with CO₂ up to 10MPa, 70°C for 5h. After acetylation, BC, with their surface partially acetylated, was rinsed with ion exchange water for 30min twice. It was dried for 24h at room temperature and further dried in a vacuum at 40°C for 24h.

The acetylated BC was compression molded into sheet at 57MPa, 200°C for 20min, then the optically transparent composite was obtained. The composite was dried for 24h at room temperature and further dried in a vacuum at 40°C for 24h, prior to the following experiments (Figure 1).

Fig.1 Schematic model of fiber cross section for the preparation of the composite with surface selectively acetylated fibers.

Measurements

The degree of substitution was evaluated by using Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer (FT-IR). All the spectra were obtained by accumulation of 10 scans, with resolution of 2cm⁻¹, at 400-4000cm⁻¹. The degree of substitution was calculated from the absorbance at 1750cm⁻¹ assigned to C=O stretching with an internal standard of absorbance at 896cm⁻¹ assigned to β-glucopyranose rings.

X-ray diffraction photographs were taken with an imaging plate having a length of 29.1 mm. The CuKα radiation, generated with an RINT-2000 (Rigaku Co.) at 40 kV, 20 mA, was irradiated on the specimen from the direction perpendicular to the surface (through) and edge. The diffraction profile was detected using an X-ray goniometer with symmetric reflection geometry. The sample of for the crystallinity was obtained by crushing into small pieces in order to achieve random orientation of the crystallites. After subtracting the air scattering, the diffraction profile was curve resolved into

noncrystalline scattering and crystalline reflections using fityk multi-peaks separation software. The apparent crystallinity, X_c , was evaluated from their area ratio. The crystallite size D was estimated using Scherrer's equation:

$$D = \lambda / \beta \cdot \cos \theta$$

where $\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$, β : corrected integral width, θ : Bragg angle for the 200 reflection.

The surface and the fracture surface of the composite were observed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (JSM-5610LVS (JEOL)), at an accelerating voltage of 20 kV. Pt/Pd was deposited on the surface prior to the observation.

Differential scanning thermographs were obtained from room temperature to 350°C using differential scanning calorimeter (DSC), model Seiko Instruments DSC120 under a nitrogen atmosphere (30ml/min) and a heating rate of 5°C/min.

The tensile strength and Young's modulus of BC, the composite and CTA cast film were measured using a tensile tester, Autograph AGS-1kND (Shimadzu), with the initial length of 20mm and the crosshead speed of 1mm/min. The density of the samples was determined by floatation method. Dynamic storage modulus was measured by a dynamic mechanical analyzer, DVA-220S (ITK Ltd.) with a temperature range from -150°C to 300°C, at a heating rate of 6°C/min, a tensile frequency of 10Hz.

Thermomechanical analysis was performed using a thermomechanical analyzer, TMA-SS120S (Seiko Instruments), at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The specimen with an original length of 15 mm was subjected to a stress of 10kPa.

The optical transparency was measured by using double beam UV-vis spectrophotometer U-2000 (HITACHI Ltd.). The thickness of the sample was 50μ m.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 shows the IR spectra of BC before and after acetylated for 5h at 70°C, 100MPa in sc-CO₂. After acetylation, the adsorption of the O-H stretching band (3340cm⁻¹) decreased, and the C=O stretching band (1750cm⁻¹) appeared. These indicate that acetylation of BC was certainly progressed in sc-CO₂. The degree of acetylation was evaluated quantitatively using the band (1050cm⁻¹) of glucopyranose ring as an internal standard.

Fig.2 FT-IR spectra of BC before and after acetylation in sc-CO₂.

Figure 3 shows the relationship between the reaction time and the degree of acetylation of BC in sc-CO₂. There are three OH groups in the repeat unit of cellulose. The result indicates that 2 of 3 OHs were acetylated in a very short time, and then it was saturated.

Fig.3 Relationship between the reaction time and the degree of acetylation of BC in sc-CO₂.

Figure 4 show scanning electron micrographs and the X-ray diffraction photograph of starting BC and resulting composite. BC nanofibers and nanospaces between nanofibers were clearly observed. From the X-ray diffraction photograph (edge), BC showed plane orientation parallel to the film surface. On the other hand, these nanospaces disappeared for the composite. This indicates that BC nanofibers were completely unified, and the interface-free structure was achieved. The X-ray diffraction photograph (edge) of the composite clearly showed plane orientations of BC and cellulose triacetate (CTA) I crystallites even after compression molding.

Fig.4 Scanning electron micrographs and X-ray diffraction photographs of starting BC and resulting composite.

Figure 5A shows X-ray diffraction profiles of the BC, acetylated BC in sc-CO₂ and the composite, respectively. Starting BC shows high crystallinity with cellulose I_α rich crystal modification. After acetylation, several peaks assigned as CTA I form appeared with overlapping of original BC peaks. Especially, after making the composite, the intensity of CTA I became very strong, while the main peaks of BC, located at $2\theta = 22.5^\circ$, remained in the profile. These indicate both CA and residual cellulose coexist in the composite. The results of the curve fitting were superimposed on the figure 5B for BC, acetylated BC in sc-CO₂ and the composite, where the cellulose crystalline reflections and noncrystalline scattering were shown with the green area, the light green area, respectively. The CTA I crystalline reflections and noncrystalline scattering were shown with the pink area, the light pink area, respectively. The noncrystalline scattering of cellulose and CA was expressed with the yellow area. The fitted results coincided very well with the observed profiles.

Fig.5 X-ray diffraction profiles and the curve fitting of BC acetylated BC in sc-CO₂ and the composite.

Table 1 shows the apparent crystallinity, X_c and the crystallite size D (nm). The X_c value greatly decreased by the acetylation of BC and it does not increased after compression molding. The crystallite size of CTA increased with the compression molding of acetylated BC in $sc\text{-CO}_2$ and the crystallite size of BC decreased with acetylation. This indicates that the crystallites of cellulose were converted into crystallites of CTA I and amorphous CA including cellulose diacetate and monoacetate, then the crystallites of CTA I increased during compression molding.

Table 1 Crystallinity X_c and crystallit size D of BC, acetylated BC in $sc\text{-CO}_2$ and the composite.

	Crystallinity	Crystallit size D (nm)		
	X_c (%)	$2\theta = 7.6^\circ$	15.9°	22.5°
BC	67.9	—	—	6.1
Acetylated BC in $sc\text{-CO}_2$ (5h)	18.0	3.9	3.7	3.9
Composite (5h)	19.3	8.0	7.0	—

Figure 6 shows the DSC thermographs of BC, acetylated BC in $sc\text{-CO}_2$, composite and CTA cast film. Compared with acetylated BC in $sc\text{-CO}_2$, the melting endotherm of

Fig.6 DSC thermographs of BC, acetylated BC in $sc\text{-CO}_2$, the composite and CTA cast film. the composite increased and the peak temperature shifted to higher temperature. These

also indicate the crystallite size of CTA I increased during compression molding.

Figure 7 shows the tensile strength and Young's modulus of BC, the composite and CTA cast film. BC possesses very high Young's modulus and the tensile strength. Compared with BC, these values were lower for the composite. However, Young's modulus (9.3GPa) and tensile strength (117.9MPa) of the composite were higher than those of conventional CTA film (Young's modulus: 3GPa, tensile strength: 90MPa). These suggest that the core cellulose plays an important for the reinforcement of the composite.

Fig.7 Young's modulus and tensile strength of BC, the composite and CTA cast film.

Figure 8 shows the temperature dependence of the dynamic storage modulus (E') of BC, the composite and the CTA cast film. BC possesses high storage modulus from -150°C to 300°C. The E' value of CTA cast film abruptly decreased at glass transition temperature (around 200°C), then increased again with temperature. This is due to recrystallization of CTA. With further increase of temperature, finally the film reached the melting temperature (around 290°C). In contrast, the storage modulus of the composite remained high from -150°C to 300°C.

Fig. 8 Temperature dependence of the storage modulus (E') of BC, the composite and CTA cast film.

Figure 9 shows the thermal expansion behavior of the BC, the composite and CTA cast film under load. The thermal expansion coefficient evaluated from these samples. BC is well known to possess very low thermal expansion. The thermal expansion coefficient of BC is 5.4ppm. Compare with this value, that of the composite was relatively high, however, it remained as 14ppm. It suggested that the composite possessed very high dimension stability.

Fig.9 Thermal expansion behavior of BC, the composite and CTA cast film under 10kPa.

Figure 10 presents the UV-vis spectra and the appearance of BC, acetylated BC in sc-CO₂, the composite and CTA cast film. The CTA cast film is well known to be very transparent as an optical film. While, BC is opaque even after acetylation. Compared with them, the composite is very transparent. These observations suggest interface free structure for the composite, the CA surrounding the core BC fiber became a matrix, which filled in the spaces between the BC nanofibers.

Fig.10 UV-vis spectra and optical transparency of BC, acetylated BC in sc-CO₂, the composite and CTA cast film, respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

The surface of BC fibers was acetylated under supercritical carbon dioxide (sc-CO₂) condition without using organic solvent. The cellulose nanofibers, with their surface being selectively acetylated, were compression molded into the composite. This new type all-cellulose composite was found to possess high optical transparency, high mechanical properties, high heat resistance and dimension stability. It was also found that the crystallites of CTA I form were plane orientated and increased during compression molding. In addition, this composite is totally composed of sustainable cellulosic resource and biodegradable after the service, which gives it advantages with regard to disposal, composting, and incineration.

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